

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING TRADITIONAL AND DIGITAL CHANNELS IN THE PROMOTION OF HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICES

Musaev B.Sh.

Independent researcher of the Samarkand Institute
of Economics and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10650329>

Abstract: Promotion of higher education services based on digital technologies, using the latest digital technologies to provide educational services to actual consumers (students, their parents, professors, administrators and other partners) and potential consumers (applicants and their parents), employers, etc.) is to deliver information in real time using internet marketing and digital marketing opportunities. This article covers the issue of promoting higher education services through traditional and digital marketing channels. More emphasis is placed on digital marketing channels.

Keywords: traditional marketing channels, digital marketing channels, marketing communications, promotion, Digital marketing tools.

Introduction.

The capacity of the global educational services market exceeds 100 billion dollars per year. Therefore, 50-70 billion dollars will be allocated to higher education services. Taking into account the growth of trade in education services, the World Trade Organization (WTO) has included trade in education services in the list of services regulated by the provisions of the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS). Since educational services are becoming an increasingly profitable sector of the economy, competition is increasing not only among higher education institutions, but also among countries. In particular, the international mobility of students, which is one of the priority directions of the development of the higher education system, allows further expansion of the export of educational services. In this regard, countries such as the USA, Great Britain, France, Germany, China and Australia are taking the lead. Increasing competition in the global educational services market necessitates greater use of marketing, especially promotional tools in attracting target audiences.

Many of the world's leading HEIs cover the costs of marketing services from their own budgets. At the same time, digital transformation processes are taking place in the marketing of educational services. The use of digital technologies in the promotion of higher education services has a significant

impact on the effectiveness of higher education institutions. Because the target audience of higher education services, i.e. consumers and potential consumers, are active users of the website and social networks. We are witnessing that the world's leading and famous HEIs are promoting themselves through extensive use of their website, social media pages and other means of promotion.

We can see that financial and academic independence is being given to public higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, and healthy competition between higher education institutions has arisen as a result of the entry of the private sector into the market of higher education services. Therefore, the issue of increasing the competitiveness of higher education institutions operating in Uzbekistan is becoming urgent. We know from world experience that the only way to increase competitiveness in all areas of production and service is the extensive use of marketing communications, that is, promotion.

Literature analysis on the topic

Many researchers have conducted their research on the promotion of higher education services. In particular, O.S. Batalova put forward such an opinion in his research. "As a result of the development of the educational services market, competition between higher education institutions appears and continues to increase [3]. Consumer demands and target audience are always changing. This increases the need to advertise and promote their services in higher education institutions." In fact, this theory was also observed in the field of higher education in Uzbekistan. Since 2016, the increased focus on education has resulted in healthy competition among higher education institutions. The requirements of learners are changing day by day. That is, if earlier, due to the small number of admission quotas, they did not apply for the fields of study they were interested in, but instead applied for the fields of study with a high chance of admission, today's applicants want to study at the HEIs of their interest, which provide prestigious and high-quality education. This increases the need for higher education institutions to promote and promote their services.

Currently, higher education institutions around the world are paying great attention to promoting their services. Because, future students began to pay attention to the choice of a higher educational institution and the direction of education. G. Krayukhina describes promotion as follows: "promotion is a set of activities aimed at informing potential consumers about the advantages of the product and inducing their desire to buy" [7]. In the promotion of higher education services, attention should be paid to strengthening the

communication and promotion of information aimed at drawing the attention of potential consumers to the advantages of higher education services.

In the promotion of higher education services, it is necessary to pay serious attention to increase the effectiveness of sales through various promotional activities aimed at the interested parties of higher education institutions mentioned by F. Kotler and Fox, that is, to the audience that can be contacted.

E.I.Bulin-Sokolova in her research on the issue of promotion of higher education services states that "the main achievements of marketing in higher education are related to the use of modern technologies for advertising and promotion of educational services." In its research, Hanover Research, "Despite the fact that HEIs place great importance on open days and other similar events in attracting new students, the means of promoting higher education services through digital technologies show that they are the most effective" [4]. According to C. Maslowsky, another foreign expert, "the website remains a very important tool for marketing promotions among higher education institutions and their various stakeholders, while focusing on the effective use of social media marketing (SMM) opportunities." necessary" . From the opinions of these researchers, it can be concluded that in today's era of advanced information and communication technologies, it is necessary to widely use digital technologies, i.e. internet marketing, digital marketing opportunities, in the promotion of higher education services.

Our Uzbek scientists and young specialists are also conducting their scientific research on the current issues of promotion of higher education services based on digital technologies and digitization of higher education services. For example, according to the opinions of S.S. Gulyamov, R.Kh. Ayupov, M.Q. Abdullaev, "... at present, the tasks of transition to the digital economy before universities and other higher education institutions are transverse: directions and specializations announced in advance One of the most urgent tasks is to expand the set of programs along with the preparation of bachelor's and master's degrees and create the necessary conditions for students to acquire the skills and knowledge required by the digital economy [12]. We can conclude from this that it was mentioned that higher educational institutions should pay attention to the fact that the graduates of higher education institutions not only have thorough knowledge of their specialty, but also master the skills and knowledge required by the digital economy.

Analysis and results

The characteristics of the educational process in higher educational institutions and their tasks before the society and the economy are changing. Currently, HEIs in the world are competing with each other to attract students, leading professors and financial resources. In such a healthy competitive environment, the HEIs that keep up with the times, choose their development path and take advantage of digital marketing opportunities are gaining an advantage over other HEIs.

One of the main advantages of digitization in HEIs is to further increase student engagement. By using digital tools such as online learning platforms, social networks and mobile applications, universities can further increase students' interest in learning. Digitization also provides opportunities for universities to use new teaching methods such as gaming and virtual reality. These methods are easily used in interactive learning experiences to explain complex concepts and theories to students.

Higher education institutions use traditional and digital marketing channels and tools to promote their educational services. Traditional and digital marketing channels used to promote higher education services are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Traditional and digital marketing channels and tools for promoting higher education services

Traditional marketing channels	Digital marketing channels	Digital marketing tools
Media advertising	Computers and tablets	New media, media +
Sales promotion	Smartphones	E-mail
Public relations	Smart gadgets	Contextual advertising
Personal selling	Websites and blogs	Banner advertising
Outdoor advertising	Social networks	Targeted advertising
Place of sale	Video hosting	Retargeting
Fairs and exhibitions	POS terminals, video cameras	Local advertising
Direct Marketing (Offline)	Local networks	Guerrilla and viral advertising on the Internet
Guerrilla and viral marketing	Digital television	SMM (social media)
Packaging, package	Interactive screens	Advertising on social

		networks
Sponsorship	Game consoles	SEO (on-site organic promotion)
Licensing	Self-service terminals	Mobile Marketing, Display Advertising, Blogging
Service	QR code of advertisements in magazines and posters	Digital Art
Entertainment events		Send SMS
Special souvenirs		Affiliate marketing
Marketing mix		QR codes

The main goal of promoting higher education services is to achieve a competitive advantage in a competitive environment, and any HEI strives to be the best among competitors, and after achieving this task, it tries to become a leading HEI (Figure 1).

This strategy is changing today in the context of digitalization. Digital transformation in global higher education sets the future roadmap for sustainable education management strategies. Digital transformation can be seen as a driving force for HEIs to gain competitive advantages (Figure 2). Therefore, creating a competitive advantage strategy in higher education, the concept of creating a competitive advantage is struggling with global phenomena such as digital transformation globalization, information exchange, digitization and social media in most of the global networks.

Figure 2. Digitization strategies of higher education institutions in a competitive environment

In a competitive environment, digitization strategies of higher education institutions accelerate the process of creating competitive advantages. Also, the wide use of these developed strategies and the fulfillment of the expectations of students and their parents (acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies) should not be neglected.

CONCLUSION

One of the important directions of digitization of educational services is the implementation of communicative relations in the electronic environment when providing the offered services to the target audience (consumers of educational services). Communicative relations of the educational institution with the market of educational services are manifested in the orientation of the educational institution to the market with its services and messages about them. It is through the digitization of these communication links that the digitization of the promotion of educational services can be achieved.

In general, when promoting higher education services based on digital technologies, the marketing department of educational institutions should focus on solving the following main tasks:

development of high-quality educational content for basic and additional professional education programs of e-learning and mixed education using distance learning technologies in accordance with customer needs and state orders and conveying information about it to the target audience;

monitoring the quality of provided educational services in terms of compliance with the standards of service provision (volume of education, requirements for results, conditions of service provision) in terms of the level of satisfaction of consumers with the quality of educational programs;

preparation for advertising and sales of educational services using digital technologies;

promotion of educational services by the educational institution through the formation of various Internet-marketing tools, including SMM and sales channels;

analysis of the results of promotion and sales of educational services;

setting requirements for academic and pedagogical staff, the level of development of their professional digital competences.

In Uzbekistan, as in all branches and fields, comprehensive measures are being implemented in the field of education for the wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies. Conceptual frameworks for the digitalization of educational services, especially the development of higher education services based on digital technologies, have been created and these processes are being improved year by year.

The legal, social, and methodological aspects of the formation and development of the promotion of higher education services based on digital technologies can be considered at 2 different levels:

1. The following practical works have been carried out to adapt the state higher education institutions to the conditions of today's digital economy: academic and financial independence has been granted to many state HEIs, free exchange of educational services has been established, the private sector has entered the market of higher education services, and cooperation with foreign higher education institutions in various directions has been carried out. that cooperations are being carried out, etc.

2. Procedures, standards, certificates and conditions for offering educational services and products in accordance with the market situation of higher education institutions in internal and external activities.

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